

M-ERA.NET
NanOx4EStor

Data Management plan

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This is Version 2.

Further updates will be released throughout the project's lifetime, and the most recent version can always be found on the project's Website. To find it, click [here](#).

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1. Introduction and objective

This document is the data management Plan (DMP) for the NanOx4Estor project, which has received funding from the Joint Call 2021 of the M-ERA.NET3, an ERA-NET Cofund supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 958174. This DMP is developed under the Task 2: Dissemination, exploitation and outreach activities of Work Package 1 Project Management, dissemination and results exploitation. It has been produced following the EC Open Research Data Pilot guidelines and it will be a live evolving document throughout the duration of the project, being updated when there are significant changes.

The DMP details how the NanOx4Estor project data will be managed during and after the project, by describing the data management life cycle for the research data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the project. NanOx4Estor follows the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” for the research data, keeping some or even all research data generated in the project closed.

NanOx4Estor follows the FAIR approach – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable – for research data, including information on:

- details of data types that will be produced and handled during and after the project
- preliminary list of expected datasets
- description of methodology and standards
- how data will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use
- how it will be curated and preserved.

2. Data summary

2.1 Purpose of the data (collection and generation)

NanOx4Estor project will generate and collect data during the planned work to develop novel and highly-efficient supercapacitors based on (pseudo-)binary oxide thin films, with improved energy storage density (ESD) and number of charging cycles at the same time, for energy storage (ES) applications. To do so, each work package has a critical role to play, and will collect data for the purposes of:

- developing wake-up free (pseudo-)binary oxide thin films, fabricated by PVD processes, with optimized ferroelectric and ES properties through (i) strain, (ii) interface and (iii) dead-layer engineering.
- Design, fabrication and prototyping of an ES supercapacitor with high ESD, operating temperature, and stability.
- Modelling of material ferroelectric properties and growth process.
- validation and testing of develop devices.
- general project reporting and dissemination (images, graphics, reports)

Experimental and simulation data will be generated from the different WP's. This data, along with other derived data, literature review, etc. will be structured into information and uploaded to NanOx4Estor main storage system on Google drive. Compilation and analysis of this information will result in knowledge, which will be disseminated in the shape of reports, scientific articles, scientific presentations, accessible to public and private sector organisations. Public data will be disseminated through different online services, including NanOx4Estor website (<https://inl.cnrs.fr/projects/nanox4estor/>) and social media. Once data is structured and analysed, it will also be made publicly available on the zenodo platform

(<https://zenodo.org/communities/nanox4estor/>). Third parties will be able to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate data and information generated or derived throughout the project, according to NanOx4EStor privacy and data protection requirements and dissemination strategy.

2.2 Types of data

Given the NanOx4EStor aim, different types of data coming from multiple sources will be collected, processed and/or generated, consisting mainly – but not exclusively – of:

- **Project management data;** used for internal management of the project and its partners. It includes minutes, mailing lists or protocols among other types of datasets.
- **Experimental data:** from labs and equipment, can often be reproduced. It includes datasets with stakeholders' inputs about production and collection, sorting, recycling and end-of-life qualities and properties of the materials. Experimental data includes environmental and technical information obtained under experiments, sensors, etc.
- **Simulations and technical data:** It is obtained from models. It can usually be reproduced if the input data is known. Simulations and technical data include material properties, physical models, among other types of data.
- **Derived data:** including compiled data from other sources or case studies. It includes data derived from databases generated after mining data or statistical analysis, reports that use NanOx4EStor generated data, among other types of data.

2.3 Data formats

The DMP describes the data that will be generated by NanOx4EStor project and how it will be published. This document is nevertheless written when most tasks are yet to be developed. Therefore, new data formats may appear during the project development. If significant changes arise, the DMP will also be updated.

The DMP follows the EC Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP). Therefore, it must be possible for third parties to access the data generated (in its various formats) during the project's development and in the future. Formats that allow the use of open source software are prioritised, as it ensures that re-usability of the data in the future. Moreover, the specific software needed to view or edit the datasets is to be specified in their metadata information. If multiple software are available for one data format, open source is preferred and should be mentioned. Most data types, including project management, experimental, simulations and derived data, will use mainly – but not exclusively – the following formats to store data:

- **Spreadsheets (xlsx):** It's very common to store and process information in spreadsheets, for example Microsoft Excel. This data can often be used immediately, given the data descriptions in the rows and columns.
- **Comma/tab Separated Values (csv, tsv):** Tsv, csv files can be a very useful format because it is compact and thus suitable to transfer large sets of data with the same structure.
- **Text Documents:** Formats like DOCX, RTF, ODF, or PDF are appropriate for certain kinds of documents, e.g., scientific journals, deliverables, reports, etc. Templates may be used whenever possible, so that displayed data can be re-used.
- **Presentation (.ppt):** PPT is a file extension for a presentation file format used by Microsoft PowerPoint. The popular presentation software is commonly used for project slide shows.
- **Plain Text (TXT):** Plain text documents (.txt) are chosen because they are very easy to read and process via plain text parsers. They generally exclude structural metadata.

- **Image or photo formats (.jpg, .png):** Image file formats are composed of digital data in one of these formats that can be rasterized for use on a computer display or printer.
- **JavaScript Object Notation (JSON):** JSON is a simple file format that is very easy for any programming language to read.
- **Extensible Markup Language (XML):** XML is a widely used format for data exchange. It offers good opportunities to preserve the data's structure and how files are built while also allowing developers to write parts of the documentation in with the data without interfering with how they are read.
- **compressed files (zip):** zip is a widely used format for data compression.

Derived data used for knowledge dissemination will be accessed through online platforms, which includes the following formats – but not only - to store data:

- **Hypertext Markup Language (HTML):** Nowadays much data is available in HTML format on various sites.
- **Video formats (avi):** A video file format is a type of file format for storing digital video data on a computer system.
- **Scalable Vector Graphics (.svg):** It is an Extensible Markup Language (XML)-based vector image format for two-dimensional graphics with support for interactivity and animation. It can be used and viewed with several software, including open source.

2.4 Origin of data

The majority of them will come from software used for simulations, experimental setups and equipment used. Data may also be collected from other sources, such as literature reviews, online sources, workshops, meetings and events, previous research projects, open source platform, legal documents and policies.

2.5 Data storage and sharing

To manage the data generated within NanOx4EStor, and allow the partners (and other researchers) to share them with each other, suitable storage media shall be used to comply with European privacy legislation. All possible datasets will be uploaded and maintained on a cloud-operating server (NanOx4EStor GoogleDrive). This platform will be the main system for storage of active research and project management data. The primary account holder is held by the coordination team and Access is limited to consortium members.

In order to reach the research and professional community, additionally to the main storage system, all public data will be made available on zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/communities/nanox4estor/>) during NanOx4EStor project.

Some of the existing and ongoing project datasets will be stored at the premises of the owning consortium partners, including software, tools and models. It is the responsibility of the partner to ensure that such software complies with the General Data Protection Regulation principles.

2.6 Data Utility

Open Research Data from NanOx4EStor will allow that other researchers can make use of that information to validate the results, thus being a starting point for their investigations, as expected by the EC through its open access policy.

3. FAIR data

NanOx4EStor will make their research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), to ensure it is soundly managed.

3.1 Making data Findable, including provisions for metadata

The key to making data findable is equipping datasets with metadata that meets basic standards and adheres to uniform, consistent schema. Provisions and actions that shall be taken to ensure the discoverability of NanOx4EStor data include:

- Accompanying datasets with properly structured and accurate metadata, according to FAIR data principles specified above.
- Providing proper documentation identifying their content and potential uses
- Making data identifiable by using standard identification mechanisms (e.g. DOI, where applicable)
- Publishing papers and reports with references to the data

The data must be described in a clear and detailed way to facilitate its understanding and reuse by others. Dataset names will include version numbers, starting with v01 for the raw data. Datasets will be named according to the following convention, using the project name, title, version number, year and month: NanOx4EStor _<datasetTitle>_<versionNo.>_<YYYY_MM>.

zenodo uses Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) making data and metadata citable and easily discoverable. DOI is resolvable, persistent and globally unique. Data files are versioned, each version has its own unique DOI. Metadata will facilitate effective searching and discovery of the data via the internet. For metadata creation, metadata schemas such as Dublin Core, DDI, and DataCite are used, which contain the following elements:

Metadata element	Description	Requirements	Notes
Dataset Persistent ID	DOI	Mandatory	Automatically Assigned
Publication Date	Dataset Publication Date	Mandatory	Automatically Assigned
Title	Dataset title	Mandatory	
Author	Author of the document	Mandatory	
Identifier Scheme	Author ID (e.g. ORCID)	Advisable	
Contact	Name of the contact person	Mandatory	
Description	Description of the dataset	Mandatory	
Subject	Domain specification	Mandatory	
Keyword	Keywords	Advisable	
Related Publication	Publication related to the deposited data	Advisable	
Notes	Additional information	Define case by case...	
Depositor	Person who deposits data	Advisable	
Deposit Date	Date of deposit	Advisable	
Grant Information	Funder and grant information	Advisable	
Software	Information about software used to collect, process or reuse data	Advisable	
Data Sources	Information about the source of the data collection	Advisable	
Others		Define case by case...	

3.2 Making data openly Accessible

NanOx4EStor results that are to be publicly available will be made accessible via zenodo an open source repository. Whenever possible, open datasets will be shared in a format accessible with open source software. UMINHO will manage the upload and submission of the files to the NanOx4EStor dataset (<https://zenodo.org/communities/nanox4estor/>) created in the zenodo open repository, although such files are to be provided by the partner responsible of the task associated to each file within the scheduled deadlines. Furthermore, in order to maximize project dissemination, some results are likely to be published in scientific journals and NanOx4EStor website.

Zenodo is a Data Repository to share, publish and manage research data generated and collected by the activity of researchers and in the research units of the University of Minho. A persistent identifier (DOI) is issued to every published record. This is a top-level and a mandatory field in the metadata of each record which helps to make uploads easily citable. Files uploaded will be retained online for the next 10 years at least. Metadata can be exported in several standard formats such as JSON, Dublin Core, DDI, DataCite Metadata Schema. It also provides analytics of uploaded information which will be used for analysing dissemination impact.

3.3 Making data Interoperable

Most of the data produced in the project will be fully available for others to re-use. To allow data exchange and re-use, all data will be saved in the most interoperable data format possible (.see section 2.3), so it is expected that they will be easily used by external parties (researchers, institutions, organisations,etc.).

3.4 Increase data Re-use (through clarifying licenses)

Use and re-use is subject to the license under which the data objects were deposited. Data will be made available for re-use with at least a CC-BY licence at the latest upon the publication of research results. This means it will be published together with the release of preprints if possible, and at latest on publication of the peer-reviewed article analyzing the respective data. All openly accessible datasets will remain re-usable for at least 10 years.

Restricted access can be configured in zenodo, where users may deposit restricted files with the ability to share access with others if certain requirements are met. These files will not be made publicly available, and sharing will be made possible only by the approval of depositor of the original file. This is not planned to be used NanOx4EStor, since the repository will be used to upload public information, but may be considered if a specific need is identified.

Data to be published will be subject to quality assurance procedures. The NanOx4EStor consortium will ensure that all shared data is consistent with quality standards required to publish in peer-reviewed journals. To the best of our abilities, we will describe the data collection and analysis procedures in sufficient detail to allow reproducibility by trained professionals in the respective project reports or research papers. As a general measure of quality assurance, all analyses and deliverables undergo an internal review process involving at least two professional researchers from the consortium partners.

4. Allocation of resources

Most of this FAIR initiative will not involve direct costs such as licenses, software or hardware since open source third parties servers and technologies will be used to host public data (see Section 3.2). Nevertheless, it will require spending time in managing such data (receiving, selecting, adapting, uploading, etc.) which has been contemplated within the management activities of both the project and the dissemination activities (WP1). Although the final upload to the repository and/or website will be performed by UMINHO, each partner is to deliver the required files to be uploaded within the agreed deadlines.

Some activities with a direct cost associated have been contemplated (such as publications in scientific journals under payment, attendance to specific events, etc.) in order to maximize NanOx4EStor dissemination. This cost has already been contemplated within travel and other goods/services costs associated to each partner.

5. Data Security

NanOx4EStor will work with different types of data and it may be classified into some groups:

- Internal data: this is the data that each partner works individually within the framework of NanOx4EStor (reports, papers, software algorithms, etc.). Each partner has measures and procedures implemented (secure storage, periodic backups, malware detection, etc.) to ensure Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability.
- Transferred data: this is the data/information that is transferred within NanOx4EStor consortium, for example deliverables preliminary versions, specification documents, simulation data, experimental measurements, etc. This data is stored and shared within consortium via Google Drive. Access to the cloud is only possible with valid credentials and access rights for the folder in question. For transfer to the cloud, data is encrypted.
- Published data: this is the data/information that is published in the website and/or the zenodo institutional Dataverse repository. The former will be operative during the project duration and information on how the repository manages the information is included in Section 3.2, supports restrictions to limit the use of or access to data that cannot be publicly accessible and provides a backup copy for safekeeping.

6. Ethical Aspects

No personal data will be collected for project purposes. Thus, no ethical or legal issues are expected regarding data sharing since no private data is expected to be included in the information that will be published.